

Light My Fire: A Roentgenogram of Cyberstalking Cases

Ioana VasIU[†]
Lucian VasIU^{††}

Introduction

Cybercrime is “an aggregate term for a collection of acts committed against or through the use of computer data or systems.”¹ Acts that can be included under the “cybercrime” category are those in which “computer data or systems are the object against which the offence is directed, as well as those in which computer or information systems form an integral part of the modus operandi of the offence.”² Examples of the latter include the use of computers for personal or financial gain or harm, as well as content-related offenses.³

Technological advances have significantly expanded the opportunities for criminal behavior with respect to content-related offenses, such as cyberthreats in violation of 18 U.S.C. § 875(c);⁴ stalking through

[†] LL.B. (1991), Babeş-Bolyai University; D.J.S. (1994), Babeş-Bolyai University. Professor Ioana VasIU is a member of the Faculty of Law at Babeş-Bolyai University and Coordinator of the Cybercrime Research Unit.

^{††} M.B.A. (2001), Ph.D. (2005). Dr. VasIU is an expert in information systems security and cybercrime.

This Article is part of a large-scale research on cybercrimes, including *Break on Through: An Analysis of Computer Damage Cases*, 14 PGH. J. TECH. L. & POL'Y 158 (2014) and *Riders on the Storm: An Analysis of Credit Card Fraud Cases*, 20 SUFFOLK J. TRIAL & APP. ADVOC. 185 (2015).

¹ Thirteenth United Nations Congress on Crime Prevention and Criminal Justice, Workshop 3: Strengthening Crime Prevention and Criminal Justice Responses to Evolving Forms of Crime, Such as Cybercrime and Trafficking in Cultural Property, Including Lessons Learned and International Cooperation, ¶ 14, U.N. Doc. A/CONF.222/12 (Feb. 2, 2015), https://www.unodc.org/documents/congress/Documentation/A-CONF.222-12_Workshop3/ACONF222_12_e_V1500663.pdf.

² *Id.*

³ See United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, *Comprehensive Study on Cyber-crime*, at 17-18 (Draft Feb. 2013), http://www.unodc.org/documents/organized-crime/UNODC_CCPCJ_EG.4_2013/CYBERCRIME_STUDY_210213.pdf (discussing the definition of cybercrime). “[C]ontents . . . includes any information concerning the substance, purport, or meaning of that communication.” 18 U.S.C. § 2510(8).

⁴ See *United States v. Elonis*, 730 F.3d 321, 325-26 (3d Cir. 2013) (reciting how the defendant posted threats on his Facebook page).

electronic means;⁵ sextortion;⁶ victim luring;⁷ enticement of a person under the age of sixteen years to engage in sexual activity, in violation of 18 U.S.C. § 2425;⁸ sex trafficking;⁹ “distribution of sexually explicit images or videos without the consent of those featured”;¹⁰ or communication of threats to injure the reputation of another, with intent to extort money in violation of 18 U.S.C. §§ 875(d).¹¹

“Stalking is a widespread phenomenon and describes a pattern of intrusive and threatening behavior leading to the victim’s perception of being harassed or rendered fearful.”¹² “Cyberstalking . . . aims to humiliate, control, frighten, manipulate, embarrass, get revenge at, or otherwise harm the victim.”¹³ In some cases, the illegal behavior can span a very

⁵ See Monique C.M. Leahy, *Proof of Cyberstalking and Cyberbullying*, 134 AM. JUR. PROOF OF FACTS 3D, 115 (2016) (defining cyberstalking).

⁶ “Sextortion” is a form of blackmail characterized by threats that aim to humiliate the victim by posting sexual images or audio recordings online. See, e.g., *Backlund v. Stone*, No. B235173, 2012 WL 3800883, at *2 (Cal. Ct. App. Sept. 4, 2012); Tracy Webb, *The Brave New World of Cyber Crime Investigation and Prosecution*, 19 NEXUS: CHAP. J. L. & POL’Y 77, 80-81 (2013) (discussing potential criminal ramifications of “sexting” among high school students).

⁷ See, e.g., *Doe No. 14 v. Internet Brands, Inc.*, No. 12-56638, 2016 WL 3067995, at *2 (9th Cir. May 31, 2016) (involving two rapists who used a website to lure the victim to a fake audition, where they drugged, raped, and recorded her for a pornographic film).

⁸ See *United States v. Giordano*, 442 F.3d 30, 38 (2d Cir. 2006) (describing how defendants used phone conversations to solicit sexual activity with underage minors).

⁹ See *Jane Doe No. 1 v. Backpage.com*, 817 F.3d 12, 17 (1st Cir. 2016) (involving victims who were trafficked via Backpage advertisements and, as a result, were raped numerous times).

¹⁰ See Cynthia Barmore, Note, *Criminalization in Context: Involuntariness, Obscenity, and the First Amendment*, 67 STAN. L. REV. 447 (2015) (“obscenity law can and should be used to criminalize revenge porn within the boundaries of the First Amendment”).

¹¹ See *United States v. Coss*, 677 F.3d 278, 281 (6th Cir. 2012) (The defendants created two fictitious personas, used for communications in which the perpetrators claimed to be a seventeen-year-old girl, impregnated by the recipient of the communication. The defendants claimed to have compromising photographs, and threatened to sell those photos to a tabloid unless the victim purchased the photographs.).

¹² Harald Dressing et al., *Stalking Behavior—An Overview of the Problem and a Case Report of Male-to-Male Stalking During Delusional Disorder*, 35 PSYCHOPATHOLOGY 313 (2002).

¹³ Alexandra Katehakis, *Cyberstalking: The Fastest Growing Crime*, PSYCH. TODAY (Mar. 10, 2015), <https://www.psychologytoday.com/blog/sex-lies-trauma/201503/cyberstalking-the-fastest-growing-crime>.

long time, sometimes lasting several decades.¹⁴ Cyberstalking is a specific form of stalking¹⁵ that involves the use of technology as the means and the medium to instigate psychological violence against another person.¹⁶

There is no generally accepted definition of cyberstalking; moreover, there is significant overlap between the definitions of “cyberstalking,” “cyber-harassment,” and “cyber-bullying.”¹⁷ The European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, in a study on violence against women, considers the following acts to be cyberstalking: “sending emails, text messages (SMS) or instant messages that are offensive or threatening; posting offensive comments about the respondent on the internet; sharing intimate photos or videos of the respondent on the internet or by mobile phone.”¹⁸

Digital technology allows cyberstalkers to not only post harmful or obscene messages, but also take on a victim’s identity,¹⁹ even from a pre-

¹⁴ See *United States v. Shrader*, 675 F.3d 300, 311-12 (4th Cir. 2012) (explaining that stalking may consist of many separate acts which cumulatively cause the victim great emotional distress).

¹⁵ Bradford W. Reynolds, *A Situational Crime Prevention Approach to Cyberstalking Victimization: Preventive Tactics for Internet Users and Online Place Managers*, 12 CRIME PREVENTION & COMMUNITY SAFETY 99 (2010).

¹⁶ Anne Bonewit & Emmanuella de Santis, *The Issue of Violence Against Women in the European Union*, 17 (2016); European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, *Violence Against Women: An EU-Wide Survey*, 81 (2014), <http://fra.europa.eu/en/publication/2014/violence-against-women-eu-wide-survey-main-results-report>; Bradford W. Reynolds & Christine M. Englebrecht, *The Fear Factor: Exploring Predictors of Fear Among Stalking Victims Throughout the Stalking Encounter*, 59 CRIME & DELINQUENCY 788, 791 (2013); Bradford W. Reynolds et al., *Stalking in the Twilight Zone: Extent of Cyberstalking Victimization and Offending Among College Students*, 33 DEVIANT BEHAVIOR, 1 (2012); ALISON M. SMITH, PROTECTION OF CHILDREN ONLINE: FEDERAL AND STATE LAWS ADDRESSING CYBERSTALKING, CYBER-HARASSMENT, AND CYBERBULLYING, CONG. RESEARCH SERV. 4 (2009).

¹⁷ Jacqueline D. Lipton, *Combating Cyber-Victimization*, 26 BERKELEY TECH. L.J. 1103, 1107-08 (2011); Kate E. Schwartz, *Criminal Liability for Internet Culprits: The Need for Updated State Laws Covering the Full Spectrum of Cyber Victimization*, 87 WASH. U. L. REV. 407, 411 (2009); Andrew M. Henderson, *High-Tech Words Do Hurt: A Modern Makeover Expands Missouri’s Harassment Law to Include Electronic Communications*, 74 MO. L. REV. 379, 381 (2009); Matthew C. Ruedy, Comment, *Repercussions of a MySpace Suicide: Should Anti-Cyberbullying Laws be Created?*, 9 N.C. J.L. & TECH. 323, 326 (2008).

¹⁸ European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, *supra* note 16, at 87.

¹⁹ Schwartz, *supra* note 17, at 415.

teenager.²⁰ Cyberstalking represents a violation of the fundamental human rights to life, liberty, and security, and can amount to a very significant interference with the victims' privacy, family, or property. Even though cyberstalking does not involve physical contact with the victim, it can nevertheless severely torment a victim.²¹

As numerous cases show,²² the victims of stalking commonly experience serious psychological harm,²³ which "often results in the victim experiencing post-traumatic stress disorder, anxiety, sleeplessness, and sometimes, suicidal ideations."²⁴ Such cases present the real risk of physical violence and even homicide, especially among prior married or cohabiting partners.²⁵ Although certain "content-related offenses, particularly those concerning child pornography, show widespread criminalization,"²⁶ cyberstalking, for a number of reasons, remains an under-prosecuted offense.

The criminal phenomenon of cyberstalking is difficult to quantify,²⁷ as data on cyberstalking is still in its early stages.²⁸ Even though stalking

²⁰ See Laura L. Myers, *Girl, 12, Gets Probation in Cyber-Stalking Case* (July 13, 2011, 6:04 PM), <http://www.reuters.com/article/us-crime-girl-cyberstalking-idUSTRE76C74C20110713>.

²¹ *Stalking and Domestic Violence*, Report to Congress, U.S. DEP'T OF JUSTICE 3 (2001).

²² See Part I, *infra*.

²³ Opposition to Defendant's Motion to Dismiss Indictment, for Franks Hearing and to Suppress Evidence at 4, *United States v. Cassidy*, 814 F. Supp. 2d, 574 (2011) (No. RWT-11-0091), 2011 WL 7762638; Dreßing Harald et al., *Cyberstalking in a Large Sample of Social Network Users: Prevalence, Characteristics, and Impact Upon Victims*, 17 CYBERPSYCH., BEHAV. & SOC. NETWORKING 61 (2014) ("The negative impact of cyberstalking on the victims' well-being appears similar to that of offline stalking.").

²⁴ *Remsburg v. Docusearch*, 816 A.2d 1001, 1007 (N.H. 2003).

²⁵ See, e.g., *United States v. Shrader*, 675 F.3d 300, 303, 311 (4th Cir. 2012) (describing violence committed by the defendant toward relatives and friends of the defendant's former girlfriend); *United States v. Matusiewicz*, 84 F. Supp. 3d 363, 365-66 (D. Del. 2015) (involving a defendant who stalked and later killed his ex-wife).

²⁶ United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, *supra* note 3, at xxi.

²⁷ Andrew King-Ries, *Teens, Technology, and Cyberstalking: The Domestic Violence Wave of the Future?*, 20 TEX. J. WOMEN & L. 131, 137-38 (2011).

²⁸ Notable, in this regard, are the efforts of Working to Halt Online Abuse (WHOA). See *Online Harassment/Cyberstalking Statistics*, WORKING TO HALT ONLINE ABUSE, <http://www.haltabuse.org/resources/stats/index.shtml> (last visited Oct. 18, 2016) (noting the difficulties of collecting accurate cyberstalking data).

“is a serious and dangerous problem in [the digital] society,”²⁹ such data collection difficulties cause the crime to be frequently overlooked.

In the last decade, however, as the result of a number of high profile cases that ended tragically for victims, cyberstalking has received increased attention from policy makers and researchers.³⁰ Despite this attention, this criminal phenomenon remains one that is not very well understood.³¹ This lack of knowledge becomes especially evident when considering the rapidly evolving technology or perpetration methods, such as stalking apps,³² anonymous and spoofed SMS messages,³³ facial

²⁹ Amicus Curiae Brief in Support of United States’ Opposition to Defendant’s Motion to Dismiss at *3, *United States v. Cassidy*, 814 F. Supp. 2d, 574 (No. 11-cr-00091-RWT).

³⁰ Aily Shimizu, *Domestic Violence in the Digital Age: Towards the Creation of a Comprehensive Cyberstalking Statute*, 28 BERKELEY J. GENDER L. & JUST. 116, 117 (2013); Eugene Volokh, *One-to-One Speech vs. One-to-Many Speech, Criminal Harassment Laws, and “Cyberstalking”*, 107 NW. U. L. REV. 731, 732-35 (2013); Christopher Young, *A First Amendment Defense to the Federal Cyberstalking Statute in the Age of Twitter*, 9 WASH. J.L. TECH. & ARTS 53, 61 (2013); John B. Major, Note, *Cyberstalking, Twitter, and the Captive Audience: A First Amendment Analysis of 18 U.S.C. § 2261A(2)*, 86 S. CAL. L. REV. 117, 128-29 (2012); Megan Rowan, *When Words Hurt More Than “Sticks and Stones”: Why New York State Needs Cyberbullying Legislation*, 22 ALB. L.J. SCI. & TECH. 645, 647-48 (2012); Ellen Kraft & Jinchang Wang, *An Exploratory Study of the Cyberbullying and Cyberstalking Experiences and Factors Related to Victimization of Students at a Public Liberal Arts College*, 1 INT’L J. TECHNOETHICS 74, 77 (2010); Michael Salter & Chris Bryden, *I Can See You: Harassment and Stalking on the Internet*, 18 INFO. & COMM. TECH. L. 99, 99-100 (2009); Naomi Goodno, *Cyberstalking, a New Crime: Evaluating the Effectiveness of Current State and Federal Laws*, 72 MO. L. REV. 125, 127 (2007); Kris Mohandie et al., *The RECON Typology of Stalking: Reliability and Validity Based Upon a Large Sample of North American Stalkers*, 51 J. FORENSIC SCI. 147, 148 (2006).

³¹ See, e.g., Emma Short et al., *The Impact of Cyberstalking*, 3 STUDIES IN MEDIA AND COMM’N 23 (2015) (“[I]t is unknown whether cyberstalking constitutes a separate criminal phenotype or if the use of technology has just been added to the armaments of the traditional stalker.”); Matt R. Nobles et al., *Protection Against Pursuit: A Conceptual and Empirical Comparison of Cyberstalking and Stalking Victimization Among a National Sample*, 31 JUST. Q. 986 (2014) (“Cyberstalking is a relatively understudied area in criminology.”); Nicolle Parsons-Pollard & Laura J. Moriarty, *Cyberstalking: Utilizing What We Do Know*, 4 VICTIMS & OFFENDERS 435 (2009) (noting “there is much more that we do not know about cyberstalking”).

³² See Danielle Keats Citron, *Spying Inc.*, 72 WASH. & LEE L. REV. 1243, 1245-46 (2015) (discussing the capabilities and the potential negative consequences of stalking apps).

³³ Graeme Horsman & Lynne R. Conmiss, *An Investigation of Anonymous and Spoof SMS Resources Used for the Purposes of Cyberstalking*, 13 DIGITAL INVESTIGATION 80 (2015).

recognition technology,³⁴ or e-mail phishing,³⁵ which give perpetrators increased capabilities and can inflict far-reaching effects on victims.

Based on the study of about three hundred American court cases, this Article presents a comprehensive examination of the main perpetration and litigation aspects involved in cyberstalking cases. Part I, based on the study of cases brought to courts or reported in press releases, notes the essential perpetration aspects of the phenomenon. Part II explains the elements of the federal cyberstalking statute. Part III reports and discusses the main litigation aspects of cyberstalking charges in violation of 18 U.S.C. § 2261A(2). Finally, this Article discusses the implications for cyberstalking criminalization, research, and litigation.

I. Characteristics of Cyberstalking

In a myriad of cyberstalking cases, the perpetrator and the victim were acquainted. They met on a variety of online sites (such as an online roommate matching service,³⁶ an Internet card game,³⁷ lesbian chat rooms,³⁸ a Craigslist advertisement for adult services³⁹) or real world settings (such as a restaurant,⁴⁰ a city bar,⁴¹ a gym,⁴² a housing

³⁴ Kirill Levashov, *The Rise of a New Type of Surveillance for Which the Law Wasn't Ready*, 15 COLUM. SCI. & TECH. L. REV. 164, 167-68 (2013).

³⁵ See Former U.S. State Department Employee Sentenced to Over Four Years in Extensive Computer Hacking, Cyberstalking and "Sextortion" Scheme, U.S. DEP'T OF JUSTICE (2016), <https://www.justice.gov/usao-ndga/pr/former-us-state-department-employee-sentenced-over-four-years-extensive-computer> (The perpetrator engaged in "a widespread, international computer hacking, cyberstalking and 'sextortion' campaign, designed to force victims to provide . . . personal information as well as sexually explicit videos of others.").

³⁶ *People v. Sucic*, 928 N.E.2d 1231, 1235 (Ill. App. Ct. 2010).

³⁷ *United States v. Rose*, 315 F.3d 956, 957 (8th Cir. 2003).

³⁸ *Marczeski v. Law*, 122 F. Supp. 2d 315, 316-17 (D. Conn. 2000).

³⁹ *People v. Corleone*, No. D052816, 2009 WL 1077189 at *1 (Cal. Ct. App. Apr. 22, 2009) (unpublished decision).

⁴⁰ *Cyberstalker Sentenced to 10 Years in Prison*, U.S. DEP'T OF JUSTICE (2016), <https://www.justice.gov/opa/pr/cyberstalker-sentenced-10-years-prison>.

⁴¹ *United States v. Jordan*, 591 F. Supp. 2d 686, 700 (S.D.N.Y. 2008).

⁴² Mary Wisniewski, *Illinois Sheriff Admits Misconduct in Cyber Stalking Case Resigns*, REUTERS (Sept. 11, 2014, 7:09 PM), <http://www.reuters.com/article/us-usa-illinois-cyberstalking-idUSKBN0H62L420140911>.

complex,⁴³ a cell phone store,⁴⁴ a University,⁴⁵ a training workshop for sex coaching,⁴⁶ and a vocational program⁴⁷). In a notably smaller number of cases, perpetrators did not know the victim previously. This category of cases involved offenders that sought a romantic or sexual relationship,⁴⁸ aimed to expose the victim's confidential information and various property to third parties,⁴⁹ or intended to terrorize the victim.⁵⁰

Cyberstalkers generally aim to exercise control over a victim through various forms of stalking behavior.⁵¹ Offenders usually intend to frighten or torment their victims, inflicting mental anguish through contemptible communications in order to force the victims to do something against their will.⁵² To accomplish this torment, perpetrators engage in a course

⁴³ *People v. Chase*, No. 09CA1908, 2013 WL 979519, at *1 (Colo. App. Mar. 14, 2013).

⁴⁴ *People v. Cavazos*, No. A124274, 2010 WL 1858139, at *1 (Cal. Ct. App. May 11, 2010).

⁴⁵ *United States v. Infante*, 782 F. Supp. 2d 815, 816 (D. Ariz. 2010).

⁴⁶ *Carle v. Gardos*, No. A138979, 2014 WL 4470834, at *4, fn. 3 (Cal. Ct. App. Sept. 11, 2014).

⁴⁷ *People v. James*, No. A124954, 2010 WL 2555630, at *1 (Cal. Ct. App. June 25, 2010).

⁴⁸ *See People v. Costales*, 2d Crim. No. B215915, 2010 WL 2044637, at *1-2 (Cal. Ct. App. May 25, 2010) (The victim, a musician, had an "an open profile" MySpace account used to market her music, on which the defendant posted sexually suggestive messages.); *United States v. Crisman*, No. CR 11-2281 JB, 2011 WL 5822731, at *1-2 (D.N.M. Nov. 15, 2011) (involving an employee who stole a customer's information at Best Buy to cyberstalk the customer he found attractive).

⁴⁹ *See Indictment at 24-29, United States v. Lazar*, No. 1:14-cr-213, 2014 WL 2623606 (E.D. Va. 2014).

⁵⁰ John Annese, *FBI: Stalker Terrorized Harry Potter Fan Author, a Former Staten Island Advance Reporter, for Years* STATEN ISLAND LIVE (July 18, 2013, 3:01 PM), http://www.silive.com/news/index.ssf/2013/07/fbi_stalker_terrorized_harry_p.html.

⁵¹ Amicus Curiae Brief in Support of United States' Opposition to Defendant's Motion to Dismiss at *4, *United States v. Cassidy*, 814 F. Supp. 2d, 574 (No. 11-cr-00091-RWT).

⁵² *See U.S. DEP'T OF JUSTICE, MANHATTAN U.S. ATTORNEY CHARGES OPERATOR OF LUXURY EYEWEAR WEBSITE WITH CYBERSTALKING, THREATENING, AND DEFRAUDING HIS CUSTOMERS* (2010), <https://www.justice.gov/sites/default/files/criminal-ccips/legacy/2012/03/15/borkerArrest.pdf> (Customers of an online store that sold counterfeit and low quality products and made unauthorized charges were "subjected . . . to a campaign of aggressive, obscene, and intimidating conduct" after complaining to the store owner.); *United States v. Walker*, 665 F.3d 212, 221 (1st Cir. 2011) (In a

of conduct that often involves persistent application of contemptuous, imperious, or blackmailing tactics.⁵³ According to one cyberstalking study, the duration of the criminal conduct varies significantly, ranging from one day to several years,⁵⁴ and in certain cases leading to physical injuries or even murder.⁵⁵

Additional cyberstalking tactics include posting disparaging misinformation about the victim on Facebook;⁵⁶ sending e-mails and texts containing death threats⁵⁷ or sextortion threats,⁵⁸ making statements

child custody battle, the defendant composed e-mails containing derogatory words, such as “whore” or “bitch,” along with threats to harm the victim, and forced his child to send the e-mails.)

⁵³ See *United States v. Savader*, 944 F. Supp. 2d 209, 210 (E.D.N.Y. 2013) (By hacking the victims’ online accounts, the defendant “obtained compromising photos of the victims,” which “would be shared with parents, employers, boyfriends or other members of the community unless the perpetrator’s demands were met.”); *United States v. Petrovic*, 701 F.3d 849, 852-53 (8th Cir. 2012) (The defendant informed the victim that he secretly taped their sexual encounters and would post the videos on his website—along with information on the sexual abuse the victim suffered, her suicidal thoughts and tendencies, and her family’s secrets—unless the victim resumed their relationship. He subsequently demanded \$100,000 to shut down the website.)

⁵⁴ See Leroy McFarlane & Paul Bocij, *An Exploration of Predatory Behaviour in Cyberspace: Towards a Typology of Cyber Stalkers*, 8 FIRST MONDAY (Sept. 1, 2003), <http://www.ojphi.org/ojs/index.php/fm/article/view/1076/996>.

⁵⁵ *United States v. Matusiewicz*, 84 F. Supp. 3d 363, 365 (D. Del. 2015).

⁵⁶ *In re Civil Commitment of Brouillette*, No. A13-1426, 2014 WL 902766, at *1 (Mich. Ct. App. Mar. 10, 2014).

⁵⁷ See *United States v. Humphries*, No. 12 Cr. 347(RWS), 2013 WL 5797116, at *2 (S.D.N.Y. Oct. 28, 2013) (The defendant “threatened the [victim] with a horrific death and also sent . . . gruesome photos of body parts, corpses, sexual torture and other images.”); *State v. Hemmingway*, 825 N.W.2d 303, 304-05 (Wis. Ct. App. 2012) (The defendant sent threatening e-mail and text communications to his ex-wife, and previously said to her, “I have not killed anyone in a long time. I don’t know who’s going to be first, you or me.”); *United States v. Bowker*, No. 4:01CR441, 2010 WL 1539964, at *1 (N.D. Ohio Apr. 16, 2010) (The defendant sent to the victim photographs with verbal captions, one referring to the victim as “being shot with a pellet gun.”); *United States v. Grob*, 625 F.3d 1209, 1212 (9th Cir. 2010) (involving a defendant who sent his ex-girlfriend a large number of threatening e-mails and text messages along with photographs of dismembered or deceased women).

⁵⁸ See U.S. DEP’T OF JUSTICE, MICHIGAN MAN CHARGED WITH CYBERSTALKING AND ATTEMPTED SEXUAL EXPLOITATION OF MINOR VICTIMS (2012), http://www.justice.gov/usao/nyw/press/press_releases/Allen3.pdf (noting the offender told victims that, unless they undressed and engaged in sexual acts, naked pictures of the victims would be released online).

conceived to insult, alarm,⁵⁹ or embarrass the victim;⁶⁰ or even posting photos, names, addresses, and phone numbers of victim's children on websites soliciting sexual activity.⁶¹ One cyberstalker extensively distributed graphically sexual and threatening communications to a victim's family, co-workers, and fellow church members.⁶²

Cyberstalkers' motivations vary widely, from revenge and hate to erotic obsessions. A significant number of cyberstalking cases involve former intimate partners.⁶³ In *United States v. Sayer*,⁶⁴ the defendant posted video clips of his ex-girlfriend on adult pornography websites, depicting sexual acts performed by the victim during their relationship, along with the victim's name and address.⁶⁵ The defendant also created fictitious online advertisements and social media profiles with the victim's name, through which men were invited "to come to her home for sexual encounters."⁶⁶ Following those postings, a plethora of men reached the victim's location, seeking sexual encounters,⁶⁷ terrifying the victim, and instilling the "fear that she would be raped or assaulted."⁶⁸

In *People v. Corleone*,⁶⁹ the defendant sent the victim threatening e-mails and demeaned individual members of her family after the victim

⁵⁹ *People v. Casarez*, No. A123927, 2010 WL 2695671, at *4 (Cal. Ct. App. July 8, 2010) (involving a defendant who sent the victim an e-mail titled "How is my dirty little whore, I mean girl, no, I guess I do mean slut," containing the text "[d]id I mention I tested HIV positive?").

⁶⁰ *Vrasic v. Leibel*, 106 So. 3d 485, 486 (Fla. Dist. Ct. App. 2013) (involving the transmission of a naked photograph of the victim to those in the victim's list of contacts).

⁶¹ *United States v. Rose*, 315 F.3d 956, 957 (8th Cir. 2003).

⁶² *United States v. Conlan*, 786 F.3d 380, 384 (5th Cir. 2015).

⁶³ See, e.g., *United States v. Osinger*, 753 F.3d 939, 941 (9th Cir. 2014); *United States v. Petrovic*, 701 F.3d 849, 852 (8th Cir. 2012); *State v. Franklin*, 166 Wash. App. 1041, at *1 (2012).

⁶⁴ No. 2:11-CR-113-DBH, 2012 WL 1714746 (D. Me. May 15, 2012).

⁶⁵ *Sayer*, 2012 WL 1714746, at *2.

⁶⁶ *Id.*

⁶⁷ See *United States v. Sayer*, 748 F.3d 425, 432 (1st Cir. 2014) ("[M]an after man showed up at my house. It didn't matter the time of day; . . . I couldn't open my windows to let the fresh air in. I couldn't keep my blinds open to light. I felt scared to walk 25 feet out to my car. No longer was I afraid of just [Sayer]; I was afraid of any man who came near me because he was a potential predator.").

⁶⁸ *Sayer*, 2012 WL 1714746 at, *1.

⁶⁹ No. D052816, 2009 WL 1077189 (Cal. Ct. App. Apr. 22, 2009).

requested to stop their intimate relationship.⁷⁰ The defendant went further, and created a MySpace page where he portrayed the victim “as a prostitute, whose mother was her ‘pimp.’”⁷¹ The defendant also posted a Craigslist solicitation with the victim’s photograph, claiming that the victim “was ‘hooking’ and invited men to ‘take advantage’ of her.”⁷² The victim received additional threatening communications, including a frightening text message from an unknown source.⁷³

Similarly, in *People v. Rosa*,⁷⁴ after their approximately ten-year marriage ended, the defendant threatened to kill the victim claiming he would “put a bullet between her eyes.”⁷⁵ The defendant also placed nude photographs of his former wife online, taken during their marriage, and advertisements that the victim was keen to meet men and perform oral sex.⁷⁶ As a result of the postings, the victim received numerous phone calls and visits at her workplace from men inquiring about the ads.⁷⁷

Cyberstalkers also employ covert electronic surveillance. They can use computer contaminants to spy on a victim’s online activity, or Global Positioning System (GPS) technology to track the location or movement of victims.⁷⁸ To conceal their activities, perpetrators will often use proxy servers located in foreign countries.⁷⁹

⁷⁰ *Corleone*, 2009 WL 1077189, at *1.

⁷¹ *Id.*

⁷² *Id.* at *2.

⁷³ *Id.* (“I have been hired by Frankie Corleone to drive to San Diego, track you down and beat you down to the point of disfigurement.”).

⁷⁴ No. F063748, 2013 WL 941728 (Cal. Ct. App. Mar. 12, 2013).

⁷⁵ *Rosa*, 2013 WL 941728, at *1.

⁷⁶ *Id.* at *2.

⁷⁷ *Id.*

⁷⁸ See *Federal Trade Commission v. Cyberspy Software, LLC*, No. 6: 08-cv-1872-Orl-31GJK, 2009 WL 2386137, at *1 (M.D. Fla. July 31, 2009) (The defendant utilized RemoteSpy, a kind of “software known as ‘spyware,’ which is used to secretly monitor the activity occurring on any computer on which it has been installed.”); *United States v. Curley*, 639 F.3d 50, 54 (2d Cir. 2011) (The defendant placed a GPS device on victim’s vehicle, and used an Internet site to track the device’s movement.); *Maddalena v. Toole*, No. 2: 13-cv-4873-ODW (Rzx), 2013 WL 5491869, at *1 (C.D. Cal. Oct. 1, 2013) (The defendant installed spyware on the victim’s laptop and work computer and a GPS device on the victim’s car, effectively tracking every electronic and physical movement of the victim.).

⁷⁹ *Vaughan v. Ky. Army Nat’l Guard*, No. 3:15-6-GFVT, 2016 WL 1633048, at *1 (E.D. Ky. Apr. 21, 2016).

The consequences of cyberstalking can be very serious. Victims of cyberstalking can develop Post Traumatic Stress Disorder,⁸⁰ be in constant fear for their life, have to change their job or place of residence, suffer anxiety attacks,⁸¹ or fear being, raped, tortured, or murdered.⁸²

II. Criminalization of Cyberstalking

A. Observations

Digital technology allows for several forms of emotional or psychological violence. One very concerning form, that can significantly disrupt the lives of the victims, is cyberstalking. Although a relatively new criminal phenomenon, cyberstalking is criminalized in virtually all of the United States and European Union states.⁸³ There are differences, however, with respect to the elements of the offense, such as the intent required (general or specific), the interpretation of the “credible threat” requirement,⁸⁴ and the type of fear instilled (for example, fear of death or bodily injury).⁸⁵

As noted by one commentator, the *mens rea* of stalking can vary:

Intentionally or purposely: the stalker has a clear foresight of the consequences of his/her actions; Knowingly: the stalker knows, or should know, that the results of his/her actions are reasonably certain to occur; Recklessly: the stalker foresees that particular consequences may occur and proceeds with the given conduct, not caring whether those consequences actually

⁸⁰ See *Maddalena*, 2013 WL 5491869, at *1.

⁸¹ *Id.* at *7.

⁸² See *United States v. Humphries*, No. 12 Cr. 347 (RWS), 2013 WL 5797116, at *3 (S.D.N.Y. Oct. 28, 2013); *United States v. Bowker*, No. 4:01CR441, 2010 WL 1539964, at *4 (N.D. Ohio Apr. 16, 2010).

⁸³ Katharine Quarmby, *How the Law is Standing up to Cyberstalking*, TECH & SCIENCE (Aug. 13, 2014, 6:08 AM), <http://www.newsweek.com/2014/08/22/how-law-standing-cyberstalking-264251.html>.

⁸⁴ Merritt Baer, *Cyberstalking and the Internet Landscape We Have Constructed*, 15 VA. J.L. & TECH 154, 160-61 (2010); *State v. Kohonen*, 192 Wash. App. 567, 575-76 (App. Ct. 2016).

⁸⁵ See Suzanne van der Aa & Renée Römken, *The State of the Art in Stalking Legislation: Reflections on European Developments*, 3 EUROPEAN CRIM. L. REV. 232, at *9 (2013).

occur or not; Negligently: the stalker did not actually foresee that the particular consequences would flow from his/her actions, but a reasonable person, in the same circumstances, would have foreseen those consequences.⁸⁶

An important distinction can be made between basic and specific intent.⁸⁷ Basic intent requires that the offense is intentionally or recklessly committed, whereas “[s]pecific intent . . . is necessary only where the acts fall short of the results condemned by the Act,” according to the Supreme Court in *United States v. Griffith*.⁸⁸ The Court stated, “even if we assume that a specific intent to accomplish that result is absent, [the defendant] is chargeable in legal contemplation with that purpose since the end result is the necessary and direct consequence of what he did.”⁸⁹ As Part I shows, the consequences of cyberstalking can be very negative for victims; however, a claim that the defendant did not intend to distress or frighten the victims, though relevant to their subjective intent or motive, becomes immaterial in determining whether or not the conduct could be prosecuted as cyberstalking.⁹⁰

At the state level, laws in three general categories address cyberstalking: (1) laws specific to cyberstalking, (2) general stalking laws encompassing cyberstalking by amendment, and (3) non-stalking laws that are applied to such conduct.⁹¹ Several states—including Washington,⁹² Louisiana,⁹³ and Florida—have enacted cyberstalking statutes to address

⁸⁶ *Id.* at *12-13.

⁸⁷ William Roth, *General vs. Specific Intent: A Time for Terminological Understanding in California*, 7 PEPP. L. REV. 67, 70 (1979).

⁸⁸ 334 U.S. 100, 105 (1948).

⁸⁹ *Griffith*, 334 U.S. at 108.

⁹⁰ *See id.*

⁹¹ *See* Casey O’Connor, *Cutting Cyberstalking’s Gordian Knot: A Simple and Unified Statutory Approach*, 43 SETON HALL L. REV. 1007, 1011 (2013).

⁹² WASH. REV. CODE § 9.61.260(1) (2004) (“A person is guilty of cyberstalking if he or she, with intent to harass, intimidate, torment, or embarrass any other person, and under circumstances not constituting telephone harassment, makes an electronic communication to such other person or a third party: (a) Using any lewd, lascivious, indecent, or obscene words, images, or language, or suggesting the commission of any lewd or lascivious act; (b) Anonymously or repeatedly whether or not conversation occurs; or (c) Threatening to inflict injury on the person or property of the person called or any member of his or her family or household.”).

⁹³ LA. REV. STAT. ANN. § 14:40.3(B)(1)-(4) (2010) (“Cyberstalking is action of any person to accomplish any of the following: (1) Use in electronic mail or electronic

the specific methods by which cyberstalking can occur. In Florida, “[c]yberstalk’ means to engage in a course of conduct to communicate, or to cause to be communicated, words, images, or language by or through the use of electronic mail or electronic communication, directed at a specific person, causing substantial emotional distress to that person and serving no legitimate purpose.”⁹⁴ Additionally, Florida law defines “[c]ourse of conduct’ [as] a pattern of conduct composed of a series of acts over a period of time, however short, which evidences a continuity of purpose.”⁹⁵ Though cyberstalking may not necessarily appear to be a violent act, Florida law treats it as such,⁹⁶ allowing the victim to obtain an injunction.⁹⁷ Cyberstalking becomes “aggravated” when the cyberstalking conduct involves a “credible threat” or is committed against someone under sixteen years old.⁹⁸

B. The Federal Cyberstalking Statute: 18 U.S.C. § 2261A(2)

In 1994, Congress enacted the Violence Against Women Act (VAWA) in response to the problem of violent acts against women.⁹⁹ Section

communication of any words or language threatening to inflict bodily harm to any person or to such person’s child, sibling, spouse, or dependent, or physical injury to the property of any person, or for the purpose of extorting money or other things of value from any person. (2) Electronically mail or electronically communicate to another repeatedly, whether or not conversation ensues, for the purpose of threatening, terrifying, or harassing any person. (3) Electronically mail or electronically communicate to another and to knowingly make any false statement concerning death, injury, illness, disfigurement, indecent conduct, or criminal conduct of the person electronically mailed or of any member of the person’s family or household with the intent to threaten, terrify, or harass. (4) Knowingly permit an electronic communication device under the person’s control to be used for the taking of an action in Paragraph (1), (2), or (3) of this Subsection.”)

⁹⁴ FLA. STAT. § 784.048(1)(d) (2012).

⁹⁵ See *In re* Standard Jury Instructions in Criminal Cases, 131 So. 3d 755, 759 (Fla. 2013) (referencing cyberstalking statutory language).

⁹⁶ FLA. STAT. § 741.30(1)(a) (2011); *Branson v. Rodriguez-Linares*, 143 So. 3d 1070, 1071 (Fla. Dist. Ct. App. 2014).

⁹⁷ *Horowitz v. Horowitz*, 160 So. 3d 530, 531 (Fla. Dist. Ct. App. 2015) (citing *Branson v. Rodriguez-Linares*, 143 So. 3d 1070, 1071 (Fla. Dist. Ct. App. 2014)).

⁹⁸ FLA. STAT. § 784.048(3) & (5).

⁹⁹ S. REP. NO. 103-138, at 37, 41 (1993) (proposed VAWA of 1993); see Pub. L. No. 103-322, 108 Stat. 1796, 1902-55 (1994).

2261A is an interstate stalking statute originally passed as part of the VAWA.¹⁰⁰ In 2006, Congress amended Section 2261A(2)(A) to read:

Whoever—

...
 (2) with the intent to kill, injure, harass, intimidate, or place under surveillance with intent to kill, injure, harass, or intimidate another person, uses the mail, any interactive computer service or electronic communication service or electronic communication system of interstate commerce, or any other facility of interstate or foreign commerce to engage in a course of conduct that—

(A) places that person in reasonable fear of the death of or serious bodily injury to a person described in clause (i), (ii), or (iii) of paragraph (1)(A); or

(B) causes, attempts to cause, or would be reasonably expected to cause substantial emotional distress to a person described in clause (i), (ii), or (iii) of paragraph (1)(A),

shall be punished as provided in section 2261(b) of this title.¹⁰¹

As the court in *United States v. Shrader*¹⁰² underlined,

Section 2261A(2)(A) & (B) provide for two different *mens rea* on the part of a defendant, and the *actus reus* paragraph of Section 2261A(2) provides for two different forbidden outcomes—substantial emotional distress or fear of death or serious bodily injury—that apply to the person and, in the case of fear of death or serious bodily injury, that person’s fear for his or her immediate family, spouse, or intimate partner.¹⁰³

The Section no longer requires the prosecution to prove that the defendant *intends* “for the victim to experience fear of death/injury or substantial emotional distress.”¹⁰⁴ The prosecution “can prove that reasonable fear of death/injury resulted from the defendant’s actions” or prove that the defendant caused or attempted to cause a victim “substantial emotional distress,” or would be reasonably expected to cause such distress.¹⁰⁵

¹⁰⁰ See Pub. L. No. 104-201, Div. A, Title X, § 1069(a), 110 Stat. 2422, 2655.

¹⁰¹ 18 U.S.C. § 2261A(2)(A) & (B) (2006).

¹⁰² 737 F. Supp. 2d 589 (S.D. W. Va. 2010).

¹⁰³ *Shrader*, 737 F. Supp. 2d at 595.

¹⁰⁴ See Edward J. McAndrew, *Say Hello to My Little Friend: The New and Improved Cyberstalking Statute*, 62 U.S. ATTORNEYS’ BULL. 30, 36 (2014).

¹⁰⁵ *Id.*

Section 2510 discusses several terms with specific meanings. “Harass” means “to trouble persistently or incessantly” and “imply systematic persecution by besieging with repeated annoyances, threats, or demands.”¹⁰⁶ “Intimidate” signifies acting to “frighten into submission, compliance, or acquiescence” and “implies the presence or operation of a fear-inspiring force.”¹⁰⁷ “The term ‘interactive computer service’” signifies “any information service, system, or access software provider that provides or enables computer access by multiple users to a computer server, including specifically a service or system that provides access to the Internet and such systems operated or services offered by libraries or educational institutions.”¹⁰⁸

“Electronic communication” broadly encompasses

any transfer of signs, signals, writing, images, sounds, data, or intelligence of any nature transmitted in whole or in part by a wire, radio, electromagnetic, photoelectronic or photooptical system that affects interstate or foreign commerce, but does not include— (A) any wire or oral communication; (B) any communication made through a tone-only paging device; (C) any communication from a tracking device (as defined in section 3117 of this title [18 USCS § 3117]); or (D) electronic funds transfer information stored by a financial institution in a communications system used for the electronic storage and transfer of funds.¹⁰⁹

The term “‘electronic communications system’ means any wire, radio, electromagnetic, photooptical or photoelectronic facilities for the transmission of wire or electronic communications, and any computer facilities or related electronic equipment for the electronic storage of such communications.”¹¹⁰ The term “electronic communication service” denotes “any service which provides to users thereof the ability to send or receive wire or electronic communications.”¹¹¹

¹⁰⁶ Harass, THE FREE DICTIONARY, <http://www.thefreedictionary.com/harass> (last visited Mar. 26, 2016).

¹⁰⁷ Intimidate, THE FREE DICTIONARY, <http://www.thefreedictionary.com/intimidate> (last visited Mar. 26, 2016).

¹⁰⁸ 47 U.S.C. § 230(f)(2).

¹⁰⁹ 18 U.S.C. § 2510(12).

¹¹⁰ *Id.* § 2510(14).

¹¹¹ *Id.* § 2510(15).

The definition of “course of conduct” is “a pattern of conduct composed of 2 or more acts, evidencing a continuity of purpose,” which becomes a criminal act when the conduct causes substantial emotional distress or a reasonable fear of serious bodily injury or death.¹¹² As emphasized in *United States v. Matusiewicz*,¹¹³ “[t]he jury must find that a reasonable person facing the same circumstances would react as the victim did,” which addresses “concerns that the statute could be enforced based on a specific victim’s disproportionate reaction to a perpetrator’s conduct.”¹¹⁴

For restitution purposes, “victim” is defined as “the individual harmed as a result of a commission of a crime” within 18 U.S.C. § 2261.¹¹⁵ The criminal penalties of the statute depend greatly “on the injury suffered by the ‘victim.’”¹¹⁶ These definitions are an important part of the litigation tactics used in cases involving violations of 18 U.S.C. § 2261A(2).

III. Essential Litigation Aspects

A. Required Intent

To violate the statute, one must both intend to cause the victim serious harm and actually cause a reasonable fear of death, serious bodily injury, or substantial emotional distress.¹¹⁷ Absent the “requisite emotional distress or fear by the ‘person,’” the defendant’s mere course of conduct will not suffice for a conviction.¹¹⁸

In *United States v. Infante*,¹¹⁹ the alleged victim refused to communicate with the defendant after a date.¹²⁰ The court granted the defendant’s

¹¹² 18 U.S.C. § 2261(A) & § 2266(2) (2013).

¹¹³ 84 F. Supp. 3d 363 (D. Del. 2015).

¹¹⁴ *Matusiewicz*, 84 F. Supp. 3d at 375.

¹¹⁵ 18 U.S.C. § 2264(c).

¹¹⁶ *United States v. Shrader*, 737 F. Supp. 2d 589, 595 (S.D. W. Va. 2010).

¹¹⁷ *Id.* at 591.

¹¹⁸ *Id.* at 595.

¹¹⁹ 782 F. Supp. 2d 815 (D. Ariz. 2010).

¹²⁰ *Infante*, 782 F. Supp. 2d at 816.

request for dismissal of the complaint, finding that the defendant's Facebook, e-mail, and text messages were only "in the misguided hope to renew their relationship," and not sufficiently threatening.¹²¹

In *United States v. Conlan*,¹²² on the other hand, after the victim made clear she was not interested in a romantic relationship, the defendant engaged in a prolonged campaign of hateful, threatening, and sexually charged communications—including e-mails, text-messages, social-media postings, telephone, and face-to-face interaction with the victim, her family, co-workers, and fellow church members.¹²³ The defendant asserted that the evidence was insufficient for a jury to find that he acted "with the intent to kill, injure, harass, intimidate, or place under surveillance with the intent to kill, injure, harass, or intimidate."¹²⁴ The court reasoned, however, that the "increasingly ominous tone and content of his messages" revealed the defendant's desire to subject the victim "to unwanted sexual acts, for her to die, and for a violent confrontation," providing sufficient evidence to conclude, beyond a reasonable doubt, that the defendant possessed the required intent.¹²⁵

B. Overbreadth and Vagueness Challenges

In numerous cases brought in violation of 18 U.S.C. § 2261A(2), the defendant challenged the constitutionality of the statute.¹²⁶ The Supreme

¹²¹ *Id.* at 821-22, 823.

¹²² 786 F.3d 380, 384 (5th Cir. 2015).

¹²³ *Conlan*, 786 F.3d at 384.

¹²⁴ *Id.* at 385.

¹²⁵ *Id.*

¹²⁶ See *United States v. Matusiewicz*, No. CR 12-83-1-GMS, 2014 WL 2446064, at *2 (D. Del. 2015) ("The Defendants argue that they cannot receive a fair and impartial trial in the District of Delaware because media coverage of the shootings reached 'all age groups and socioeconomic classes' . . . and was 'provided through all known media formats.'"); *United States v. Osinger*, 753 F.3d 939, 943 (9th Cir. 2014) (defendant arguing that 18 U.S.C. § 2261(A) was "facially unconstitutional because it prohibit[ed] speech protected by the First Amendment"); *United States v. Petrovic*, 701 F.3d 849, 854 (8th Cir. 2012) (involving a defendant's challenge of the statute's constitutionality on First Amendment free speech grounds); *United States v. Cassidy*, 814 F. Supp. 2d 574, 581 (D. Md. 2011) (defendant asserting that "Section 2661A(2)(A) violates the Free Speech Clause of the First Amendment because it is overbroad and implicates a broad range of otherwise constitutionally protected speech").

Court explains, “imprecise laws can be attacked on their face under two different doctrines—overbreadth and vagueness.”¹²⁷

In *United States v. Bowker*,¹²⁸ the defendant argued that the statute was facially overbroad, as it “reaches large amounts of protected speech and conduct” and “potentially targets political or religious speech.”¹²⁹ However, the court rejected the notion that “prohibition of intentionally using the Internet in a course of conduct that places a person in reasonable fear of death or seriously [sic] bodily injury” would have “a substantial sweep of constitutionally protected conduct.”¹³⁰ The court went further, noting that “[i]t is difficult to imagine what constitutionally-protected political or religious speech would fall under these statutory prohibitions.”¹³¹

In *United States v. Conlan*,¹³² the defendant argued the statute was unconstitutionally vague by failing to provide definitions of “harass” and “intimidate.”¹³³ The court noted, however, that these words were well-known and any vagueness concerns were alleviated by “easily understood terms surrounding ‘harass’ and ‘intimidate—‘kill, injure . . . or cause substantial emotional distress’—and by the statute’s scienter requirement, which narrows its scope and mitigates arbitrary enforcement.”¹³⁴

The defendants in *United States v. Sayer*¹³⁵ similarly argued that the terms “harass,” “injure,” and “substantial emotional distress” were too vague, but failed because they simply restated their overbreadth argument.¹³⁶ Courts easily find such an argument unpersuasive for such commonplace terms and with regard to stalking statutes “with sufficient definiteness that ordinary people can determine what conduct is prohibited.”¹³⁷

¹²⁷ *United States v. Bowker*, 372 F.3d 365, 378 (6th Cir. 2004).

¹²⁸ 372 F.3d 365 (6th Cir. 2004).

¹²⁹ *Bowker*, 372 F.3d at 378.

¹³⁰ *Id.* at 378-79.

¹³¹ *Id.* at 379.

¹³² 786 F.3d 380 (5th Cir. 2015).

¹³³ *Conlan*, 786 F.3d at 385.

¹³⁴ *Id.* at 386.

¹³⁵ 748 F.3d 425 (1st Cir. 2014).

¹³⁶ *Sayer*, 748 F.3d at 435.

¹³⁷ *Monhollen v. State*, 947 S.W.2d 61, 62 (Ky. Ct. App. 1997).

The vagueness of the terms “harass” or “intimidate” was raised again in *United States v. Shrader*.¹³⁸ The court emphasized that a statute cannot be declared vague “simply because it does not include the most elaborate or the most specific definitions possible,” and “when a statute fails to provide an explicit definition, we may resort to ordinary meaning and common sense.”¹³⁹ The court dismissed the defendant’s argument, as he could not “plausibly claim this string of verbs left him clueless.”¹⁴⁰

The defendant in *Shrader* also argued that the statute was void for vagueness, because it failed to explain whether every act included in “course of conduct” required a specific intent to harm.¹⁴¹ Again, the statute defines the required “course of conduct” as “a pattern of conduct composed of [two] or more acts, evidencing a continuity of purpose.”¹⁴² The prosecution is not required to “prove that each act was intended in isolation to cause serious distress or fear of bodily injury to the victim”; it suffices “to show that the totality of the defendant’s conduct ‘evidenc[es] a continuity of purpose’ to achieve the criminal end. The specific intent requirement thus modifies the cumulative course of conduct as a whole.”¹⁴³ The court further noted a requirement “that each act have its own specific intent element would undo the law’s protection for victims whose anguish is the result of persistent or repetitive conduct on the part of a harasser.”¹⁴⁴

C. Protected Speech

Although the First Amendment guarantees free speech,¹⁴⁵ the right is not absolute.¹⁴⁶ There are categories of unprotected speech, such as

¹³⁸ 675 F.3d 300, 310 (4th Cir. 2012).

¹³⁹ *Shrader*, 675 F.3d at 310.

¹⁴⁰ *Id.* at 311.

¹⁴¹ *Id.*

¹⁴² *Id.* at 309-10.

¹⁴³ *Id.* at 311.

¹⁴⁴ *Id.* at 312.

¹⁴⁵ U.S. CONST. amend. I.

¹⁴⁶ See Stuart Minor Benjamin, *Transmitting, Editing and Communicating: Determining what “The Freedom of Speech” Encompasses*, 60 DUKE L.J. 1673, 1678

“advocacy intended and likely to incite imminent lawless action, obscenity, defamation, child pornography, fighting words, fraud, true threats, speech integral to criminal conduct, and speech presenting a grave and imminent threat the government has the power to prevent.”¹⁴⁷ The prohibition on “true threats,” for example, often raised in cyberstalking cases, “protect[s] individuals from the fear of violence” and “from the disruption that fear engenders,” in addition to protecting people “from the possibility that the threatened violence will occur.”¹⁴⁸

Because the cyberstalking statute mentions means of communication, it permits questions with regard to protection of speech.¹⁴⁹ Depending on the speaker’s state of mind, as well as the circumstances surrounding the case, the same words or conduct may be criminal activity or protected speech. Numerous cases present engaging discussions on the matter of protected speech, as follows.

In *United States v. Osinger*,¹⁵⁰ after the victim refused to resume their relationship, the defendant created a fictitious Facebook page in his victim’s name that included sexually explicit photographs of her and sent e-mails containing nude photographs of the victim to her co-workers.¹⁵¹ The court rejected the defendant’s First Amendment challenge, reasoning that any “expressive aspects of Osinger’s speech were not protected under the First Amendment because they were ‘integral to criminal conduct’ in intentionally harassing, intimidating or causing substantial emotional distress” to the victim.¹⁵²

A similar defense can be encountered in *Sayer*, where the defendant, via e-mail and Internet websites, engaged in a course of conduct that

(2011) (discussing the extent of the Free Speech Clause of the First Amendment and the constraints it imposes upon the government’s ability to regulate online transmissions); Robert C. Post, *Recuperating First Amendment Doctrine*, 47 STANFORD L. REV. 1249 (1995) (asserting that “First Amendment jurisprudence seek[ing] to protect the abstract fact of communication . . . has led to a deep doctrinal incoherence”); Thomas I. Emerson, *Toward a General Theory of the First Amendment*, 72 YALE L.J. 877 (1963) (examining the ambiguity of the first amendment doctrine).

¹⁴⁷ Daniel S. Harawa, *Social Media Thoughtcrimes*, 35 PACE L. REV. 366, 380 (2014).

¹⁴⁸ See *RAV v. St. Paul*, 505 U.S. 377, 388 (1992).

¹⁴⁹ *United States v. Matusiewicz*, 84 F. Supp. 3d 363, 365 (D. Del. 2015).

¹⁵⁰ 753 F.3d 939 (9th Cir. 2013).

¹⁵¹ *Osinger*, 753 F.3d at 947.

¹⁵² *Id.*

instilled a reasonable fear of death or serious bodily injury in the victim.¹⁵³ The defendant indirectly argued that his conduct—the use of Internet postings intended to induce third parties to contact the victim for sexual encounters—was protected speech by claiming that the statute was unconstitutionally overbroad.¹⁵⁴ The court found, however, that, even assuming that the course of conduct targeting the victim involved any speech at all, such speech was not protectable.¹⁵⁵

Another discussion on the First Amendment right to speak on public concern matters can be found in *United States v. Sergentakis*.¹⁵⁶ For about three years, the defendant was employed as a purchasing manager by a charitable non-profit organization.¹⁵⁷ Subsequently, the defendant pled guilty to several criminal charges involving the allocation of his employer's contracts, and was sentenced to prison and ordered to pay \$1 million in restitution to his former employer.¹⁵⁸ The defendant was aware that the CFO (later the CEO) of the organization that employed him provided information regarding the defendant's conduct to law enforcement.¹⁵⁹ In retaliation, the defendant engaged in a resentful e-mail and online campaign of personal attacks against the victim involving allegations of rape, child molestation, and animal cruelty in violation of 18 U.S.C. § 2261A(2), for which the defendant was later prosecuted.¹⁶⁰

The *Sergentakis* defendant argued that the statements he made on websites were “protected speech on matters of public concern under the First Amendment.”¹⁶¹ Adversely, the prosecution asserted the speech was essential to the criminal conduct charged, used as the means to carry out a retaliatory harassment campaign against the victim.¹⁶² The Government also argued the defendant's speech, even if outside an unprotected

¹⁵³ *Id.* at 430.

¹⁵⁴ *Id.*

¹⁵⁵ *Id.* at 434.

¹⁵⁶ No. 15 Cr. 33 (NSR), 2015 WL 3763988 (S.D.N.Y. June 15, 2015).

¹⁵⁷ *Sergentakis*, 2015 WL 3763988, at *1.

¹⁵⁸ *Id.*

¹⁵⁹ *Id.*

¹⁶⁰ *Id.* at *1-2.

¹⁶¹ *Id.* at *3.

¹⁶² *Id.* at *4.

category, failed to “address any matter of public concern and therefore does not deserve First Amendment protection.”¹⁶³ The defendant stated his postings were based only on facts, but the court found insufficient support for this argument.¹⁶⁴

The defendant further claimed the victim was a public figure based on his executive positions; therefore, his speech should be protected.¹⁶⁵ Rejecting this contention, the court found no clear evidence of the victim’s “general fame, notoriety, or pervasive involvement in the affairs of society to warrant public-figure status for all purposes.”¹⁶⁶ The court again emphasized that, even if the victim could be considered a public figure, “the speech at issue in this prosecution is not a matter of public concern.”¹⁶⁷ Unsurprisingly, the court denied the defendant’s motion to dismiss the indictment.¹⁶⁸

Contrastingly, a cyberstalking indictment was dismissed on First Amendment grounds in *United States v. Cassidy*.¹⁶⁹ The defendant posted approximately 8,000 derogatory tweets and Internet blog postings in an intense campaign that questioned the legitimacy of the victim as the leader of a Buddhist sect, which rendered the victim fearful for her safety.¹⁷⁰ The court found the victim was a “well-known religious figure,” the subject of a “critical non-fiction book,” and the defendant’s speech “challenge[d] her character and qualifications as a religious leader.”¹⁷¹ The court further held the victim “had the ability to protect her ‘own sensibilities simply by averting’ her eyes from the Defendant’s Blog and not looking at, or blocking his Tweets.”¹⁷² Consequently, although the defendant’s speech “may have inflicted substantial emotional distress,” the indictment was directed at protected speech outside

¹⁶³ *Id.*

¹⁶⁴ *Id.* at *7 (“Everything on this website is fact . . .”).

¹⁶⁵ *Id.* at *5.

¹⁶⁶ *Id.*

¹⁶⁷ *Id.* at *6.

¹⁶⁸ *Sergentakis*, 2015 WL 3763988, at *8.

¹⁶⁹ 814 F. Supp. 2d 574, 588 (D. Md. 2011).

¹⁷⁰ *Cassidy*, 814 F. Supp. 2d at 579.

¹⁷¹ *Id.* at 583.

¹⁷² *Id.* at 585.

of the recognized exceptions.¹⁷³ Following this reasoning, the court granted the motion to dismiss the indictment.¹⁷⁴

The *Cassidy* reasoning is similar to the stance of the Electronic Frontier Foundation (EFF), which argued that the case was “about the basic freedom to express one’s thoughts to the public.”¹⁷⁵ The EFF also emphasized that as people utilize new digital technology to express their thoughts, “it is important to maintain our Constitutional guarantees at the electronic frontier.”¹⁷⁶ Following the decision in *Cassidy*, United States Attorney General Holder stated that the holding did not affect the Government’s ability to defend the constitutionality of 18 U.S.C. § 2261A(2)(A) in pertinent cases.¹⁷⁷ The Attorney General also explicitly noted that the Government could still prosecute the *Cassidy* defendant’s postings under Section 2261A(2)(B) to the extent they contained threats of physical harm.¹⁷⁸

D. Crime of Violence

For federal crimes, “crime of violence” is defined as

- (a) an offense that has as an element the use, attempted use, or threatened use of physical force against the person or property of another, or
- (b) any other offense that is a felony and that, by its nature, involves a substantial risk that physical force against the person or property of another may be used in the course of committing the offense.¹⁷⁹

In a detention hearing, one defendant, charged with violating Section 2261A(2)(A), argued that the offense “cannot qualify as a crime of violence because it does not categorically include an element involving

¹⁷³ *Id.* at 583.

¹⁷⁴ *Id.* at 588.

¹⁷⁵ Brief of Amicus Curiae Electronic Frontier Foundation Supporting the Defendant and Urging Dismissal at 1, *United States v. Cassidy*, 814 F. Supp. 2d 574 (D. Md. 2011) (No.11-cr-00091-RWT), <https://www.eff.org/ro/node/58563>.

¹⁷⁶ *Id.*

¹⁷⁷ Letter from Eric H. Holder, Attorney General, to Honorable John A. Boehner, United States Speaker of the House of Representatives (March 7, 2012).

¹⁷⁸ *Id.*

¹⁷⁹ 18 U.S.C. § 16(a)(b) (2016).

the use of force or threatened use of force as required by the definition of a ‘crime of violence’ set forth in 18 U.S.C. § 3156(a)(4)(A).¹⁸⁰ The defendant also claimed

such an offense fails to meet the alternate definition contained in 18 U.S.C. § 3156(a)(4)(B) because, by its nature, the offense does not involve a substantial risk that physical force may be used in committing the offense . . . [and] that an individual may be convicted under the statute without ever having been in the physical presence of the victim and without committing any purposeful, violent, or aggressive act.¹⁸¹

The court, however, opined that “the legislative purpose behind 18 U.S.C. § 2261A(2)(A) certainly indicates congressional intent that offenses under this section be considered crimes of violence for purposes of holding a detention hearing.”¹⁸² As Section 2261A(2)(A) is part of the Violence Against Women Reauthorization Act, it would be “illogical and counterintuitive to conclude that the Government is precluded from requesting a detention hearing in the case of an alleged offender who fails to meet the other eligibility criteria contained in 18 U.S.C. § 3142(f).”¹⁸³

E. Unit of Prosecution

The “unit of prosecution” determines the number of individual offenses the defendant has committed.¹⁸⁴ In *United States v. Shrader*,¹⁸⁵ the defendant was charged with two counts of violating Section 2261A(2) for engaging in a single course of conduct, which caused harassment and intimidation of the victim and her husband.¹⁸⁶ The defendant claimed the counts were “multiplicitous” because, under Section 2261A(2), the

¹⁸⁰ *United States v. Grooms*, No. 3:15-mj-00025, 2015 WL 1982097, at * 2 (S.D.W. Va. Apr. 29, 2015).

¹⁸¹ *Id.*

¹⁸² *Id.* at *5.

¹⁸³ *Id.*

¹⁸⁴ *See United States v. Rentz*, 777 F.3d 1105, 1117 (10th Cir. 2015) (Matheson, J., concurring).

¹⁸⁵ 737 F. Supp. 2d 589, 591 (S.D. W. Va. 2010).

¹⁸⁶ *Shrader*, 737 F. Supp. 2d at 591.

“allowable unit of prosecution” should be determined on the basis of the act or acts allegedly committed in violation of the statute, not the number of victims.¹⁸⁷

The court adversely reasoned that the statutory provision defines the “unit of prosecution” as applied to the “person,” as section 2261A(2) indicates unambiguously that the criminal act consists of not only the course of conduct, but also the *impact* of the course of conduct on the person(s).¹⁸⁸ Conduct that does not cause emotional distress or fear to the victim will not suffice for a conviction under this section.¹⁸⁹ Consequently, both charges were permissible, as they were based on a different victim, and thus, a different unit of prosecution.¹⁹⁰

F. Sentencing Departures and Variances

In *United States v. Sayer*,¹⁹¹ the defendant appealed the district court’s four-level offense enhancement based on aggravating factors under the United States Sentencing Guidelines: “(1) a longterm pattern of stalking, threatening, or harassing behavior; and (2) violation of court protection orders that [the victim] had against the [defendant].”¹⁹² Explaining its upward departure from the Guidelines range, the district court in *Sayer* stated:

[T]here are factors here that the sentencing commission simply has not considered in the guideline analysis. And they are, for example, the use of anonymous third parties to harass the victim and the extra danger that that caused . . . [where the victim] has no idea of the limits [these third parties] might go to; the effect of posting on the Internet her identity, address, intimate details, all of which, as we know, is permanent, unlike situations where stalking occurred in a different era without the Internet; the many involvements that this defendant had with law enforcement, which did not deter him until the final arrest; and the ongoing obsession that he apparently

¹⁸⁷ *Id.*

¹⁸⁸ *Id.* at 592.

¹⁸⁹ *Id.* at 595.

¹⁹⁰ *Id.* at 597-99.

¹⁹¹ 748 F.3d 425 (1st Cir. 2014).

¹⁹² *Sayer*, 748 F.3d at 431.

had even up until August of [20]11 as reflected by the letter and testimony of [Sayer's cellmate] at the detention hearing and the chilling things that the defendant was still possessing in his mind at that time.¹⁹³

The court also addressed relevant statutory sentencing factors, explaining that an “above-Guidelines sentence was needed to keep Jane Doe and the public safe from [the defendant], as well as to give [him] enough time to receive treatment so that he did not repeat his behavior with Jane Doe or in another relationship.”¹⁹⁴ The First Circuit affirmed the district court’s decision to vary upward under the federal sentencing guidelines.¹⁹⁵

The sentencing guidelines were also applied in other cases, such as in *United States v. Bowker*.¹⁹⁶ The court noted that the victim in *Bowker* experienced “profound feelings of paranoia” and altered her lifestyle drastically by changing her bank, phone number, and mailing address, and by purchasing a gun and using a security escort.¹⁹⁷ Additionally, she felt compelled to step away from a career as an on-air newscaster.¹⁹⁸ The district court in *United States v. Rose*¹⁹⁹ applied federal sentencing guidelines because it “found that [the defendant]’s conduct evidenced his intent to carry out his threats to murder [the victim]’s children.”²⁰⁰

Application of federal sentencing guidelines was considered in *United States v. Humphries*²⁰¹ due to the large number of significantly threatening messages that the defendant sent to the victim.²⁰² While free on bail, the defendant attempted to deter the victim from testifying at his trial by sending her hundreds of messages, in violation of a protective order.²⁰³ Despite the abundant threatening messages, the court found a downward

¹⁹³ *Id.* at 433.

¹⁹⁴ *Id.* at 437.

¹⁹⁵ *Id.* at 438.

¹⁹⁶ 372 F.3d 365, 390-92 (6th Cir. 2004), *vacated*, 543 U.S. 1182 (2005).

¹⁹⁷ *Bowker*, 372 F.3d at 391.

¹⁹⁸ *Id.*

¹⁹⁹ 315 F.3d 956 (8th Cir. 2003).

²⁰⁰ *Rose*, 315 F.3d at 957.

²⁰¹ No. 12 Cr. 347 (RWS), 2013 WL 5797116 (S.D.N.Y. Oct. 28, 2013).

²⁰² *Humphries*, 2013 WL 5797116, at *2, 5.

²⁰³ *Id.* at *3.

variance from the Guidelines appropriate because of the defendant's mental health issues, namely symptoms consistent with depression, PTSD, and OCD.²⁰⁴

In a number of cases, the defendant has argued that, taking into consideration certain factors, downward departures should have been applied.²⁰⁵ In *United States v. Ull*,²⁰⁶ for example, the defendant challenged the sentence, asserting that a downward departure was warranted due to her mental state.²⁰⁷ The Second Circuit noted that it was not obligated to consider expert psychiatric testimony, and that the sentence was not "substantively unreasonable," as no evidence showed that the defendant could not control her behavior.²⁰⁸ The court affirmed the sentence of the district court, as it adequately considered the necessary factors in imposing a sentence under 18 U.S.C. § 3553(a) by balancing the defendant's mental condition "with the need for promoting respect for the law, providing just punishment, deterring the defendant and others from committing similar offenses in the future, and protecting the public from further criminality."²⁰⁹

The survey of cyberstalking cases revealed no application of the "sophisticated means" enhancement.²¹⁰

Conclusion

Cyberstalking is a special form of stalking, which involves the use of digital technology as the means and the medium to inflict certain emotional effects on victims.²¹¹ As evidenced by this survey of cases,

²⁰⁴ *Id.* at *4-5.

²⁰⁵ *Osinger*, 753 F.3d at 948-49; *Sayer*, 748 F.3d at 436.

²⁰⁶ 370 F. App'x 225 (2d Cir. 2010).

²⁰⁷ *See Ull*, 370 F. App'x at 226 (A psychiatric evaluation prior to trial showed that the defendant suffered from a "[d]elusional disorder with erotomantic, paranoid and grandiose features.").

²⁰⁸ *Id.*

²⁰⁹ *Id.* at 226-27.

²¹⁰ U.S. SENTENCING COMM'N, U.S. SENTENCING GUIDELINES MANUAL § 2B1.1(b)(10)(C).

²¹¹ *See Sayer*, 748 F.3d at 430 (quoting 18 U.S.C. § 2261A(2)(A) (2012)).

cyberstalkers are a varied group of offenders with respect to age, gender, sexual orientation, marital status, and intellectual background. Cyberstalking can lead to significant and lasting psychological, economic, and even physical effects, and can be a platform for the commission of other crimes.

This Article's findings compel more research in order to better understand how to effectively respond to cyberstalking offenses. Additionally, educational programs regarding ways to protect oneself from cyberstalking attacks would reduce criminal opportunities for cyberstalkers. This Article also underlines the need for users to protect their digital privacy and computer data by using technology to block out unwanted messages, employing enhanced identity management technology, and learning how to preserve the evidence of any illegal conduct.

There is a clear need for programs or features that would flag threatening communications, and remove online postings that falsely impersonate an individual or that inflict emotional distress and/or fear to victims. An improved legal framework is also needed to better address this criminal phenomenon, specifically a more precise definition of the proscribed conduct and tougher punishment for such crimes, especially in cases of prolonged or extreme conduct. The application of the "sophisticated means" enhancement should be justified in cases where the conduct involves advanced technology or methods of concealment. Finally, as cyberstalking is an international criminal phenomenon, it should be included in the Cybercrime Convention, to facilitate cooperation in the gathering and sharing of evidence, and in the bringing of offenders to justice.